

Type 1 and Type 2 Fuzzy Logic for Enhance Wi-Fi Direct Performance in Vehicular Communication

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Abstract:

Wi-Fi Direct technology enables users to share services in groups, and support Service discovery at the data link layer before creating a P2P Group, and it can be used as a collaborative application integrated into vehicles for multimedia transfer and group configuration between V2X. Compared to cellular networks, IEEE 802.11 has expanded and integrated a stand-alone D2D solution in 5G. Wi-Fi Direct offers a high transmission data rate at a cheaper cost. However, there are numerous hurdles to using Wi-Fi Direct in vehicles, including the fact that Wi-Fi Direct communication has a relatively small coverage area, disconnection may occur multiple times, and the distance between vehicles changes often in a moving setting. Which negatively affects the quality of service delivery. Previous studies disregarded the motion and direction of moving objects.

The main contribution of this paper is to use Wi-Fi Direct among vehicles to reduce reliance on the 5G network, thereby addressing the previous challenges. In particular, the main contribution of this paper is to introduce a set of scenarios based on different speeds, directions, and distances between vehicles. The state of the packets is monitored in each scenario to compute the packets delay and loss. We present a new contribution to the services discovery by providing V2V IE with a set of services that reflect the user's interest, such as Web pages, SMS, Audio links, and Video links, using the Generic Advertisement Protocol GAS, and a comparison between the traditional P2P IE and the new V2V IE. Furthermore, the paper introduces a stable Wi-Fi Direct clustering method based on important parameters impacting the group formation, such as the location, the destination, the direction, the speed of the vehicle and the user's Interests List. Finally, we will apply and compare the two types of fuzzy systems to Solve the problem of uncertainty at the time of packet loss when transfer multimedia in vehicle: Type-1 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic T1TSFL and Interval Type-2 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic T1TSFL.

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Furthermore, the paper introduces and compares the two types of fuzzy systems to solve the problem of uncertainty at the time of packet loss when transferring services in a vehicle. At uncertainty, T2FLS performs well compared to T1FLS in terms of accuracy. Relying on T2FLS led to a lower rate of packet loss and delay because the selection of available services with a pre-determined time in the adjacent table became more accurate.

We concluded from the results of previous experiments that Wi-Fi Direct can be used with vehicles at low speeds and high speeds. In the case of low speeds, it works efficiently depending on OMNET++ results. Therefore, Wi-Fi Direct can be used in vehicle stations and work sites that use limited-speed vehicles such as Clark's machines to alert safety and provide them with information about the devices around them. Bearing in mind that the speed of devices is limited in work areas. In the case of high speeds, the results are significantly improved using the proposed Type-2 fuzzy Logic system T2FLS to model uncertainty and imprecision in a better way. In the case of increasing uncertainties, T2FLS is well performed than T1FLS in terms of precision. Relying on T2FLS has led to a decrease in the rate of Packets Loss and Delay because the selection of the available services with previously specified time in the neighboring table became more accurate and avoiding uncertainty, depending on calculating the size of the data and the WFD signal strength conjunction with the distance and speed between the vehicles.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the recommendations of the Wi-Fi Alliance [1], WFD is one of the innovative communication solutions. WFD is a peer-to-peer standard [2] that allows Wi-Fi devices to communicate directly with each other without the need for a wireless hotspot. The P2P protocol defines three distinct device functions: device discovery, service discovery, and group formation. WFD devices discover each other and form a P2P group. In each P2P group, one specific node, called the P2P GO group owner, acts as an access point AP [3]. P2P devices can exchange queries to discover available services and decide whether to continue forming the group, and the request and response message are exchanged in the service discovery process which is done using General Advertising Service (GAS) protocol frames [4]. The service discovery procedure can be used to find a list of all services offered by a P2P device [5]. WFD has become an attractive and suitable candidate for communication in a variety of application fields, such as content distribution, resource sharing, emergency communications, alert dissemination, online gaming, proximity-based advertising, and social networking. Today, WFD is not only a de facto technology for direct communications between Wi-Fi devices but also a strong candidate for D2D communications in future 5G networks, with data rates up to 250 Mbps. Thus, we can say that Wi-Fi Direct, as the latest wireless networking standard, can outperform DSRC in the near future [6-8]. Many suggestions have referred to the use of WFD in vehicles [9-14], However, no clear standard has been set for the use of WFD in vehicles. This is due to several reasons including the small area covered by WFD (not exceeding 200 meters) [15], and the speeds and directions of vehicles are variable. It should be noted that we did not compare WFD with cellular networks because the results are already known to be superior to WFD [16], and many research papers have dealt with these topics.

Several research efforts have compared WFD and DSRC and concluded that WFD has better performance than DSRC [6] [8]. These efforts, however, did not apply their results to the reality of real vehicles and measure their works in terms of different speeds and directions. The previous limitations motivate other researchers to propose a hybrid V2X system [13,14] that includes a flexible combination of the cellular network and WFD as a solution to alerts in disconnect [12]. The proposed solution, however, did not determine the effectiveness of continuing the connection if the vehicle is in motion. Because of these problems, countries have tended to use some technologies such as Wave, Cellular V2X, ITS G5, and DSRC. Based on the previous facts, most countries do not possess such expensive modern technologies [12,14]. Thus, it has become important to search for technical solutions that completely reduce the dependence on the 5G network. In this paper, we propose a system that is available to the majority and is inexpensive by employing WFDWFD. We introduce different scenarios based on OMNeT++ results, aiming at answering some of the Questions that have not been considered in much of the previous research: **Q1)** What are the optimal speeds for vehicles to make a successful connection? **Q2)** Is it possible to use WFD for multimedia transmission in a movement environment? **Q3)** Is it required that the vehicle be in the same direction? **Q4)** What time the connection is interrupted and the vehicle loses service?

Finally, we propose a Type-1 Fuzzy Logic System T1FLS and Interval Type-2 Fuzzy Logic System T2FLS to solve the problem of uncertain processing and decision-making. To this end, the work of this paper highlights the following major contributions: First, we present WFD in the style of scenarios that include the concept of WFD clusterization and Group Owner elect. Second, we implement a set of different scenarios in OMNET++ that express, in the first scenario we set the vehicle's speed at 10m/s in the direction of 180° degrees with other vehicles, and we repeated this scenario with an increase in speed until it reached 100m/s, then we changed the direction of the vehicle to 0° -180°, opposite the direction of the vehicles, and in each scenario, we monitor the state of packets delay and packets loss. We use a different speed and direction for each scenario, then compare the results of the scenarios to each other. Third, we present a new method for services discovery by providing P2P IE with a set of services that reflect the user's interest, such as Web pages, SMS, Audio links, and Video links, using the Generic Advertisement Protocol GAS, thus, the user determines the availability of the service and then decides to join the P2P Group or not. We add intent to each service so that the highest value of intent is for road safety messages based on the common Interests List in neighboring table P2P IE, and we a comparison between the results both of OMNET++, Type-1 Fuzzy Logic System T2FLS and Type-2 Fuzzy Logic System T2FLS.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In section II, we present related work to Wi-Fi Direct. In section III, the details of a scenario using WFD are integrated into the vehicle. In section IV, the details of the threshold depend on the connection of devices. In section V, determining reachability depends on the adjusted threshold of the vehicle. In section VI, predicting disconnection between vehicles over time. In section I, a WFD communication is established for transmitting a video stream request message. In section II, the implementation of IEEE 802.11 handover in OMNeT++ is discussed. In the next section, apply T1FLS and T2FLS. In section VI, results and discussion. Finally, we conclude the paper in section VII.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Several studies have been conducted to prove the effectiveness of Wi-Fi Direct. Shuhaimi, N. I *et al.* [6] compared WFD and DSCR and proposed a mathematical analysis comparing the throughput efficiency of both uniform distribution and binomial using DSRC and WFD parameters, to improve VANET's MAC performance. Similar work was proposed by Balasundram, A *et al.* [8]; however, the approach depended on single-hop and multi-hop connections and yielded the same results. Shuhaimi, N. I *et al.* & Balasundram, A. *et al.* [6, 8] concluded that WFD performed better than DSRC. However, the authors did not apply these results to real vehicles at different speeds and directions. The authors proposed a hybrid V2X system that included a flexible combination of cellular networks and WFD as a solution for offline alerts, but they did not determine the effectiveness of continuing the connection with the movement of the vehicle. [12-14]. Many studies have proposed a Group Owner GO election that aims to enhance the performance and persistence of the P2P group [3, 14, 18, 19]. Jeong, *et al.* [14] suggested the dynamic selection of P2P GO in Wi-Fi Direct, and dynamically elected owners could be replaced based on collection strategies such as battery status, user speed, and movement direction. The authors also presented a model for writing clustering algorithms to achieve effective GF. Khan, M. A., *et al.* [3] proposed an approach to determine the election of a group owner based on the generation of a group owner negotiation procedure, in which devices exchange their intent value, which represents their willingness to act as group owners.

The device with the highest intent value was chosen as the GO. Chaki, P., *et al.* [18] proposed group repair that helps maintain near-continuous contact when the Group Owner suddenly leaves the group without any prior notice and mitigates group over-reliance on the group owner GO. This concept is supported by the proposed mechanism of Dormant Backend Links to reduce the total downtime of a group. The authors implemented a DBL mechanism in a practical Wi-Fi P2P test and provided an empirical evaluation. Shahin, A. A., *et al.* [19] proposed multi-GF for efficient communication, which is a new protocol that allows WFD to dynamically cluster itself into groups and select the GO appropriately. The authors proposed an EMC scheme that allows P2P GO to be selected based on the state of the remaining battery of the device, and the EMC also allows members of premium groups to communicate. The proposed scheme was tested using an Android API.

WFD performance analysis has been of great importance in several works [20-23] due to WFD performance evaluation. Khan, M. A., *et al.* [20] introduced the implementation of WFD in the INET framework for OMNeT++, implementing key WFD actions such as discovery, negotiation, and group formation. The implementation was validated using two test scenarios. Camps-Mur, D., *et al.* [21] proposed an analysis of the delay in the formation of WFD groups, and presented the first performance analysis of WFD through real experiments and simulations, and performed it on NS-3 software. Sun, W., *et al.* [22] proposed a simple and effective scheme called random channel listening (LCR) to accelerate device discovery. The proposed scheme uses a Markov model and was examined using an NS3 simulation. Liu, K., *et al.* [23] introduced multi-hop communication in WFD among open-source Android devices and an ad hoc on-demand distance vector (AODV) reactive routing protocol. The authors implemented a routing protocol in a MANET by using multiple smartphones to enable efficient message delivery.

Several works have proposed the integration of new services with WFD for performance improvements [24-28]. Jin, M., *et al.* [24] proposed algorithm used a statistical distribution of the size of the video frames and adjusted the wake

lengths in a dynamic beacon separator. In addition, given the interdependence between video frames, the proposed algorithm ensures that a high-priority video frame is transmitted with a higher probability than other low-priority frames. Yoon, H., *et al.* [25] proposed decentralized collaborative media content streaming (DOMS) to realize flexible and scalable media content sharing by exploiting clip-based collaborative broadcasting between Wi-Fi devices. Gunda, V.G. & Kim, J., *et al.* [26,27] implemented WFD prototypes for car-to-car communication using an Android device and implemented flexible group value message formatting in service discovery using GPS for request information about distance to reduce the amount of data transmission. W. -S. Jung, *et al.* [28] proposed a new architecture that creates a self-organizing ad hoc network over WFD on a smartphone which can achieve high power efficiency for energy-constrained devices.

III. SCENARIO USING WFD INTEGRATED INTO THE VEHICLE

We support WFDapp integration into vehicles and include a communication circuit that supports a first connection method with Wi-Fi directly by other vehicles in the same periphery and a second connection method with 5G communication wider than the WFD periphery. Integration of WFD into the vehicle system leads to efficient use of WFD owing to the power of the battery and memory capacity. If the vehicle uses a mobile WFD, the P2P device must use power saving; otherwise, this may affect its discoverability [4]. The first and second connection methods may be the V2V or V2X communication methods. The first connection method is WFD communication, and the second is 5G communication. According to the environment, the vehicle obtains information from the enabled WFD connection about WFD devices at the periphery of the vehicle communication system and stores the information in the WFD memory (P2P IE) before forming a P2P Group. The WFD classifies the neighboring WFD Information and stores the results in a table configuration. For example, information about the WFD devices at the periphery of the vehicle communication system includes signal, key, and IP information. All devices in the P2P Group then communicate with each other, and the election P2P Group Owner GO acts as an AP [7]. The smart device in the vehicle has the right to request to join the group through the WFD within the coverage area of the WFD communication radius area. The smart device in a vehicle located outside the coverage area of the WFD communication radius uses 5G communication. The P2P GO group owner generates WFD information messages about available services using the GAS protocol and transmits the generated information through the WFD connection for the coverage radius. The process begins after device discovery and before the group formation GF process [29]. The Service

Table 1. Shows an example of the neighboring table configuration.

Vehicle Data					WFD Services		WFD Info.		
ID	Location	Speed	Direction	Destination	Interests List Links	Time	signal	Key	IP
1	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	video, news	xx	Good	xx	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx
2	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	image, accidents	xx	Poor	xx	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx
3	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	songs, image	xx	Excellent	xx	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx
4	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	traffic jams	xx	Weak	xx	xxx.xxx.xxx.xxx

Discovery Query frame supports different service types, which changes the content of the vendor-specific content field. The Service Discovery Query frame uses the GAS Initial Request frame as defined in IEEE 802.11[4, 30].

The WFD connection information includes at least one of the Internet protocol (IP) addresses or keys and includes at least one of the Wi-Fi simple configuration information elements (WSCIE) or peer-to-peer information elements (P2P IE) Table 1.

1. Scenario Performance In-band Handover Located within the Coverage Area

The WFDapp stores the information generated in a neighboring table configuration. After collecting data about its environment, the smart device in the vehicle will then scan Phase [4] of the neighbor table to find a suitable device to act as a P2P [5] and play the role of AP, a WFD Device associated with an infrastructure AP still needs to be in the Listen State for In-band Device Discovery. If a P2P Device wishes to connect, it will initiate Group Owner Negotiation to attempt to form a new P2P Group or send a P2P Invitation Request frame to request the P2P Device to join a P2P Group In-band [31]. In this case, Group Owner GO plays a role in the CH.

This step is called the assessment neighbor CH [32]. If the chosen CH is found within the cluster (found a suitable CH), otherwise, if the vehicle itself is best suited to be a CH, Group Owner GO will be the CH. It will proceed and affiliate with CH [33]. The WFD CH performs a handover message between the V2X and the WFD communication in the group. Cluster head CH sort the group members, and exclude and accept them into the cluster according to five parameters.

WFD CH metrics can assist in identifying the common multimedia interest list of vehicles in the group and allow vehicles access to cluster resources. The WFD CH collects similar multimedia requests in the interests list of the neighboring table. Hereafter, the first vehicle sends a message about a multimedia interest list, such as image or video information through WFD communication, and the second vehicle receives messages through the WFD connection. The WFD CH computes the interested list selection metric through WFD communication.

The WFD cluster head searches in the neighboring vehicles for user requests and receives a message from vehicles to provide interest in multimedia. If the vehicles within the cluster are not interested, this means that the cluster does not have common interests. In this case, the search scope expands to another cluster or direction towards the 5G radius r area.

2. Scenario Performance Out-band Handover Located out the Coverage Area

Vehicles have the right to choose from the first moment between using the WFD communication coverage area or expanding the coverage area to 5G communication, depending on the availability of parameters such as the vehicle's direction, speed, or distance. If the WFD service is not available in the vehicle or it is disabled, an automatic switch will be made over a wider area. Here, the search scope was in more than one cluster. The vehicle then initiates a WFD Out-of-Band channel for Device Discovery. WFD out-of-band device discovery is used to ensure that two P2P Devices agree on a common channel for GO negotiation for the GF if no suitable group exists [4]. If the Vehicle uses WFD Out-of-Band communication, then a P2P Device or P2P Group Owner uses a WFD Handover Request Message for Out-of-Band Device Discovery. In addition, the CH does not accept the joining of the vehicle to the group owing to the lack of parameters. The vehicle then searches for another group.

IV. SCENARIO DETERMINING THE DISTANCE BETWEEN VEHICLES

The WFD determines the distance between the second vehicle and the first vehicle after a predetermined time ΔT has elapsed, determines the distance based on the current speed of each vehicle, and stores the generated information in the neighboring table configuration.

$$X + V_R \times \Delta T - V_H \times \Delta T \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), x denotes the distance between the first and second vehicles at a specific time point. V_R denotes the speed of the second vehicle, where V_H denotes the speed of the first vehicle.

Referring to Equation (1), the WFD in the first vehicle determines the distance between the second and first vehicles based on the difference between the movement distance of the second vehicle during the predetermined time ΔT and the movement distance of the first vehicle during the predetermined time ΔT .

FIG.1 WFD Network Time 1.

Referring to Fig. (1), at time T_1 , in area 1, the WFD stores the generated information in the neighboring table configuration, and smart device 0 will then scan the neighbor table to find vehicles that have the reachability to vehicle 0. Vehicles 1 to 5 have reachability from vehicle 0, which represents the group owner GO and ID in the neighboring table, indicating that there is no reachability stored in the field associated with vehicles 6 to 9, which are not located in the WFD radius r area but are located in the 5G radius r area. When vehicle 0 needs to connect by Wi-Fi directly to smart device 3, vehicle 0 determines that vehicle 3 has reachability based on cluster radius and connects by Wi-Fi directly, which is approximately 200 m [10,20]. In the case where vehicle 0 needs to connect to smart device 8, vehicle 0 determines that vehicle 8 has reachability based on the 5G area and connects by 5G communication. Smart devices within the WFD radius r area and 5G radius r area may change with time. Once the discovery process is complete, the group formation procedure begins with the detected devices.

In the standard group formation procedure, the two devices go through an election process to determine the roles of the P2P GO and the P2P client. During the GO election, each device shared an intent value to declare its desire to become a GO. The device that sends a higher intent value (ranging from 0 to 15) becomes GO and the other device becomes a client [31] [7]. A P2P Group formation procedure is initiated with the WFD Source setting GO intent to zero.

The WFD in vehicle 0 initiates a P2P GF procedure with its GO intent to indicate GO only before the GO negotiation phase of the Wi-Fi P2P connection setup [4], and it is chosen as the CH. In Fig. (2), at time T2, vehicles 8 and 9 first enter the WFD cluster area, and vehicle 3 moves to the 5G radius r area. The WFD in vehicle 0 updates the reachability field value associated with vehicle 3 in the neighboring table. WFD GO changes the reachability field from ID, indicating the existence of ID and nonexistence with respect to the vehicle 3. Vehicle 0 updates the reachability field ID associated with vehicle 8 in the neighboring table. Vehicle 0 changes the reachability field from ID, indicating nonexistence, to ID, indicating existence with respect to vehicle 8.

Vehicle 3 must disconnect from a V2V Group, indicate the intent to disconnect from a V2V Group using the de-authentication procedure [4], and A P2P GO shall not depend on receiving either indication and may determine that a client has departed for a variety of reasons. A P2P GO can disconnect a vehicle from a V2V Cluster. To disconnect a Client, a P2P GO uses the de-authentication procedure and sends a de-authentication frame to the Client if the V2V Group is established.

The WFD stores or maintains [34] information on smart devices located within the area of WFD radius r in the neighboring table. The WFD does not store information on smart devices located outside the WFD radius r area in the neighboring table. Depending on the location of the vehicle 9 at time T2, the WFD deletes the data stored with respect to the vehicle 9 in the neighboring table (P2P IE), the WFD update [35], and the reachability information of the vehicle 9. Once the P2P Group is formed, the GO continuously announces its presence by sending a beacon AP. GO must run the DHCP to allocate IP addresses to all associated clients [3]. Both the P2P GO and P2P Client can connect to another P2P Group or Wi-Fi network. Thus, a P2P Device can be a GO in one P2P Group and a client in another P2P Group or legacy network [19]. The negotiated Local IP address is used for the Layer-3 connection within the WFD IE [4], as described in the neighboring table.

FIG.2 WFD Network Time 2.

FIG.3 WFD Network Time 3.

Referring to Fig. (3), at time T3, Wi-Fi directly determines that vehicle 3 is located within the WFD area, and vehicles 5 and 9 are not located within the WFD area. Vehicle 0 changes the reachability field value of vehicle 3. In the case where there is a need for a WFD connection to Vehicle 3, Smart Device 0 attempts to reconnect to Vehicle 3. If an association is denied, a P2P IE is included in the Association Response frame containing the V2V Status [4]. WFD GO uses the information stored in the neighboring table. The vehicle 0 adds information about the Vehicles 5 and 9

to the neighboring table. According to an embodiment of Fig. (3), vehicle 0 adds reachability information about Vehicles 5 and 9 to the neighboring table (P2P IE) again. while performing V2X communication, vehicle stores, in advance, information about vehicles capable of connecting to the WFD network. WFD GO manages candidate devices by using the reachability information, thereby reducing disconnection due to frequent movements.

Herein, the importance of the neighboring table information appears because it plays a role routing table that keeps track of paths, and uses data to determine which way to forward traffic of vehicles [25] [23] [36]. Nevertheless, it may not be able to service a large number of devices. Thus there must be a maximum number of devices, to determine the optimal size of a P2P group existing with several clustering algorithms to deal with such a problem [3]. A P2P GO indicates to the connected vehicles its intention to end a V2V Group session. The unexpected departure of a P2P GO shall terminate the V2V Group session. If there are no connected V2V vehicles the P2P GO may end the V2V Group session [4]. V2V vehicles can request that the V2V Group to be restarted and use the stored V2V IE to join for additional sessions after initial formation, the required information is the MAC address of the peer device. It is called the Persistent WFD Group; such a Persistent WFD Group has a lifetime that may extend over a number of sessions until the group is dissolved [5].

V. AUDIO AND VIDEO AV STREAMING CONTROL

Layer data services include the transport of audio/video AV and the exchange of neighboring table WFD information, such as keys and protocols over IP [2]. On receipt of an RTSP Request message, the WFD in the first vehicle routes the AV stream to the second vehicle specified in the WFD services in the neighboring table contained in the RTSP Request. After the transmission of an RTSP Response message with a status code of RTSP OK, the WFD in the first vehicle sends RTSP request messages to the second vehicle about service information such as data type, data size, and signal. The WFD Session supports RTP [25] multimedia data delivery using both UDP and TCP protocols, and switching between the protocols is allowed as needed. The WFD Session was completed before starting AV streaming over the UDP. The WFD video formats were included in the WFD Service Discovery frames. The data size rate described in the neighboring table refers to the rate at which the AV size is obtained from the WFD Source. The transport stream includes information used to determine if the AV payload corresponds to [5]. Table 2.

Table 2. Illustrates video stream configuration on OMNET++.

Speed	Video Size	Threshold	SINR
(20mps, 10mps)	10MiB	10m	4dB
(40mps, 10mps)	20MiB	40m	6dB
(50mps, 10mps)	50MiB	100m	8dB
(60mps, 10mps)	100MiB	120m	10dB
(80mps, 10mps)	200MiB	180m	12dB
(100mps, 10mps)	400MiB	200m	15dB

VI. SCENARIO DETERMINING REACHABILITY DEPENDING ON ADJUSTING THE THRESHOLD OF THE VEHICLE

In Algorithm. (1), the first vehicle performs direct Wi-Fi communication. The first vehicle adjusts a threshold for determining reachability depending on the concentration of vehicles located at the periphery of the vehicle and connects to the second smart device based on reachability. In this step, the first vehicle determines the number of neighboring vehicles located at the periphery of the first vehicle. The first vehicle obtains the number of neighboring devices based on direct Wi-Fi communication. The number of neighboring devices was determined using vehicle data stored in a neighboring table. According to the area, the number of neighboring devices within the second area or second cluster radius r is greater than the number of neighboring devices within the first area or first cluster radius r . In this step, the first vehicle adjusts its threshold based on the number of neighboring devices [24].

In the case where the number of neighboring devices is large, the first vehicle decreases the threshold of the number of neighboring devices, and in the case where the number of neighboring devices is small, the first vehicle increases the threshold, which leads to a stable clustering algorithm. In this step, the WFD calculates the distance between the first and second smart devices, and if satisfies the threshold, the first vehicle determines the reachability of the second smart device based on the rest of the parameters.

When the distance to the second smart device does not satisfy the threshold, the first vehicle ends the operation.

In this step, the first vehicle transmits a request to the second smart device. Requests message data for requesting data transfer or a connection request message.

Algorithm 1: Compute Connectivity based on Threshold

- *Input: CH_i and V_i .*
- *If Distance of $V_i < \text{Threshold}$ then*
- *Connect CH_i of the V_i .*
- *Else Disconnect CH_i of the V_i*
- *Make maintain the neighboring table information of V_i .*

$$\text{for } (i \text{ to } j - 1), \{Dis(V_{i+1} - V_j) < r\} \quad (2)$$

In Equation (2), V_i denotes a first multi-hop vehicle, V_j denotes a second multi-hop vehicle, r denotes a WFD coverage area threshold, D is denotes distance, and $Dis(V_{i+1} - V_j)$ denotes the distance between the first and second multi-hop vehicle.

VII. SCENARIO PREDICTING DISCONNECTION BETWEEN VEHICLES OVER TIME

In Algorithm (2). the first vehicle performs WFD communication with the second smart device. In the case where it is predicted that the connection is to be disconnected, the WFD CH provides a notification that the connection is disconnected before the termination of the current communication service. WFD CH predicts based on the neighboring

table configuration whether the connection between the first vehicle and the second smart device will have disconnected after a predetermined time.

In this step, the first vehicle determines whether the determined distance is greater than the threshold. If the determined distance does not satisfy the threshold, the first vehicle maintains a WFD communication connection to connect with other smart devices. If the determined distance satisfies the threshold, the first vehicle receives data within a predetermined time, and the first vehicle handovers data and receives data from the second smart device [18]. Over time, because the location of the smart device within a cluster radius r changes, the WFD CH reconstructs the neighboring table configuration for multi-hop communication with a second device. The WFD CH determines whether the predetermined condition is satisfied based on the following equation:

$$\Delta T(V_i - V_j) > r \quad (3)$$

ΔT denotes a predetermined time, V_i denotes a vehicle of index i in the neighboring table configuration, V_j denotes a vehicle of index j in the neighboring table configuration, and i and j have an index that decreases as the distance from the first vehicle decreases., furthermore, denotes a vehicle that satisfies the predetermined condition in which the distance satisfies the threshold.

Algorithm 2: Compute the degree of Vehicle

- Initialize set of Vehicles as V .
- Compute the degree of Vehicle D_i .
- $Deg(D_i) = 0$.
- If (i not equal to k)
- $k = 1$.
- Repeat the step ($k = 1$) until $k = V$.

VIII. SCENARIO ESTABLISHING A WFD COMMUNICATION FOR TRANSMITTING A VIDEO STREAM REQUEST MESSAGE

In Fig. (4). the first vehicle generates the video stream request message to the second smart device, which includes WFD connection information and establishes a WFD communication connection. WFD connection information includes at least one multimedia interest list from the neighboring table configuration [35]. In this step, Service Discovery is an optional procedure in Wi-Fi Direct. The procedure started after Device Discovery and prior to the Group Formation procedure. This allows a P2P Device to advertise available services using the link layer Generic Advertisement Service (GAS) protocol [20]. In this step, the first vehicle determines whether a request acceptance message is received from the second smart device within a predetermined timeframe. When the request acceptance message is not received within a predetermined time, the first vehicle does not establish a WFD connection and ends the operation. A request acceptance message that accepts a video stream request means that a WFD connection request is accepted. The second smart device receives the video stream request message, including the WFD information. If a

request message is received within the predetermined time, the first vehicle determines whether the second smart device accepts a connection request message that satisfies the specified parameters. The WFD CH determines whether the second smart device is a smart device located in the WFD cluster radius r .

When the second smart device is not located in the WFD cluster radius, r does not establish a WFD connection and ends the operation. When the second smart device accepts the request of the first vehicle, the second smart device transmits a video stream to the first vehicle together with a connection acceptance message. The first vehicle receives the video stream along with the connection acceptance message as a response message associated with the video stream request message. If the video stream is not transmitted within a predetermined time, the first vehicle ends the reception of the video stream and the operation. When it is determined that the service is stopped, the first vehicle turns off video streaming.

FIG.4 Transmit video stream request message.

IX. SCENARIOS BASED ON DIFFERENT PARAMETERS FOR MONITORING PACKET STATUS

In this section, we will try to apply a set of scenarios to address the problems that hinder the use of Wi-Fi directly in vehicles. Here, we implement WFD in the INET Framework of OMNeT-6.0, for the test scenarios.

1) Calculation of End-To-End Delay. In Fig. (5). it was found that End-To-End Delay increases when vehicles increase their speed with a constant direction parameter. The delay was checked in speed configurations of 10, 20, 40, and 60 m/s. Then, we increased the speed of the vehicles to 100m/s and changed the direction of the vehicles; thus, the distance between the vehicles increased.

2) Calculation of Packet Loss. In Fig. (6). it was found that packet loss increased with increasing distance between vehicles. The distance between vehicles increases if one of the vehicles increases its speed, or if one of them changes direction.

3) Calculate the packet drop sum. In Fig. (7) it was found that the packet dropped owing to the location of the vehicle from the edge of the threshold. The closer the vehicle is to the edge of the threshold; more packets are dropped.

4) Calculation of the packet Received Sum. In Fig. (8) in the case of vehicle stability, the packets received an increase. Analysis of the results shows that the state of the WFD quality has an inverse relationship depending on the speed and distance between devices, which indicates that whenever one of them increases by a certain amount, the other increases with an increase that is proportional to the increase in the first and vice versa.

Table 3: Show Scenarios Vehicle End-To-End Delay based on Speed

mps	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
10	0.0272977	0.0272977	0.0272977	0.0272977
20	0.0451863	0.0451863	0.0451863	0.0451863
30	0.0640043	0.0640043	0.0640043	0.0640043
40	0	0.0903727	0.0903727	0.0903727
50	0	0.0903727	0.100246	0.100246
60	0	0.0903727	0.100246	0.114302
70	0	0	0.100246	0.134862
80	0	0	0.100246	0.147988
90	0	0	0	0.147988
100	0	0	0	0.147988

FIG.5 WFD Handover Vehicles End-To-End Delay

FIG.6 WFD Handover Vehicles Packets Loss

FIG.7 WFD Handover Vehicles Packet Drops

FIG.8 WFD Handover Vehicles Packet Size Received

Analysis of the results shows that the state of the WFD quality is inverse relationship depending on the speed and distance between devices that denotes that whenever one of them increases by a certain amount, the other increases with an increase that is proportional to the increase of the first and vice versa.

X. Proposed Type-1 and Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Handover Method

The results of the experiments on the OMNeT not showed the answer to the problem 4 above with satisfy, what time interval the connection is interrupted and the vehicle loses service? the packets loss changes dynamically with each connection. This dynamic nature of the traffic in networks [43], makes it difficult to determine time the connection is interrupted and the vehicle loss to service, this will increase uncertainty.

We have applied and compared the two types of fuzzy systems to Solve the problem of uncertainty at the time of packet loss when transfer multimedia in vehicle: Type-1 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic TITSFL and Interval Type-2 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic TITSFL.

The proposed based on two basic task: the vehicle is still into threshold for connection and this depends on the two variables of speed and distance. and quality of service QoS depends on the two variables of data size and signal. Type-1 and type-2 Takagi-Sugeno FLCs are elaborated to use the input variables attached to this behavior, which are: the distance and speed between the actually position of the vehicle and the coordinates of the threshold, and Signal and DataSize between the actually Quality of Service.

FIG.9 Speed and Distance for T2TSFL

FIG.10 Speed and Distance for T1TSFL

In this work, Type-1 and Type-2 Fuzzy Logic System include the neighboring table of vehicle such as Vehicle Data, WFD Services, WFD Information's. **In phase1**, the input variables of the Vehicle Data Are Speed (VS) and Distance (VD), the output is Threshold (TH) states which express to connection. The input variables of the WFD are Data Size (DS) and Signal (SG), the output is Quality of Services (QoS) which express to Handover.

The linguistic fuzzy labels are: The input Speed (VS) divides to five parameters Gaussian MFs (VS - Very Slow, S - Slow, M - Medium, F - Fast, VF - Very Fast). The range values of the universe for Speed inputs [0 100]. The input Distance (VD) divides to five parameters triangular MFs (VNR – Very Near, NR – Near, M – Medium, FR – Far, VFR – Very Far). The range values of the universe for Distance inputs [0 200]. The output Threshold represents to three parameters Linear type MFs (Good, Medium, Bad). The input Data Size (DS) divides to three triangular MFs (DS-Small, DM-Medium, DL-Large). The input Signal (WG) divides to five triangular MFs (SX-Excellent, SG-Good,

SM-Medium, SW-Weak, SP-Poor). The output Quality of Services (QoS) represents to five parameters Gaussian MFs (Very Good – Good – Acceptable – Bad – Very Bad). The minimum and maximum values of the universe for WFD inputs and outputs [0 1].

FIG.11 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic Threshold Output

FIG.12 Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Logic QoS Output

In phase2, the input variables of Threshold represent to three parameters type MFs (Good, Medium, Bad), The input Quality of Services (QoS) represents to five parameters MFs (Very Good – Good – Acceptable – Bad – Very Bad). The Output Decision represent to three parameters (Sent – Wait – Not Sent).

FIG.13 Takagi-Sugeno T2FLS Decision Output

All system parameters are summarized in Table 4 with their corresponding forms of fuzzy membership functions.

Table 4: Membership functions: Definition of the fuzzy linguistic values of system parameters.

System Parameters (Linguistic Variables)	Linguistic Values	Linguistic values of T1FLS		Linguistic values of T2FLS		
		Params	MF Type	Params Upper	Params Lower	MF Type
Speed	Very Slow Slow Medium Fast Very Fast	[0 0.250] [0.25 0.500] [0.25 0.5 0.75] [0.5 0.75 1] [0.75 1]	trimf	[0 0 2.501 22.51 1] [2.5 22.5 27.5 47.5 1] [27.5 47.5 52.5 72.5 1] [52.5 72.5 77.5 97.5 1] [77.5 97.5 102.5 122.5 1]	[6.25 4.167 0 0.5] [6.25 4.167 25 0.5] [6.25 4.167 50 0.5] [6.25 4.167 75 0.5] [6.25 4.167 100 0.5]	trapmf
Distance	Very Near Near Medium Far Very Far	[0 0.25] [0 0.25 0.5] [0.25 0.5 0.75] [0.497 0.747 0.997] [0.75 1]	trimf	[0 0 0 50 1] [0 50 100 1] [50 100 150 1] [100 150 200 1] [150 200 250 1]	[0 0 0 25 0.5] [25 50 75 0.5] [75 100 125 0.5] [125 150 175 0.5] [175 200 225 0.5]	trimf
Threshold	Good Medium Bad	[0 50 100] [50 100 150] [100 150 200]	trimf	[0 0 1] [0 0 0.5] [0 0 0]	[0 0 1] [0 0 0.5] [0 0 0]	Linear
Signal	Poor Weak Medium Good Excellent	[0 0.250] [0.250 0.2474 0.4974] [0.25 0.5 0.75] [0.5 0.75 1] [0.75 1]	trimf	[0.1062 1 1] [0.1062 0.25 1] [0.1062 0.5 1] [0.1062 0.75 1] [0.1062 1 1]	[0.0531 1 0.5] [0.0531 0.25 0.5] [0.0531 0.5 0.5] [0.0531 0.75 0.5] [0.0531 1 0.5]	gaussmf
Data Size	Small Medium Large	[0 0.4] [0.1 0.5 0.9] [0.6 1]	trimf	[0 0.5 1] [0 0.5 1 1] [0.5 1 1.5 1]	[0 0.375 0.5] [0.125 0.5 0.875 0.5] [0.625 1 1.375 0.5]	trimf
Quality of Services	Very Bad Bad Acceptable Good Very Good	[0 0.250] [0.25 0.500] [0.25 0.5 0.75] [0.5 0.75 1] [0.75 1]	trimf	[0 0 0] [0 0 0.25] [0 0 0.5] [0 0 0.75] [0 0 1]	[0 0 0] [0 0 0.25] [0 0 0.5] [0 0 0.75] [0 0 1]	Linear

Fuzzy rule base includes fuzzy IF–THEN rules, the rules are chosen as IF (Speed is Medium) and (Distance is Near) and (Signal is Excellent) and (Data Size is Small) THEN (Quality of Services is Acceptable) All rules for fixed input values are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: illustrates (Phase1) Type-1 and Type-2 Fuzzy Logic control rules.

Distance		Very Near			Near	Medium			Far	Very Far		
Speed		VNR			NR	M			FR	VFR		
Very Slow	VS	Good	Data Size			VG	Good			Acc	Bad	
		QoS	Signal	EXT	VG	G						
				VG	VG	VG						

Slow	S	Good	G	Acc			B	VeryBad			
Medium	M	Acc	Acc	Medium		Data Size		V	VeryBad		
				QoS	Signal	M	WK				
		Acc	VB			VB					
Fast	F	Bad	B	Bad			VB	VeryBad			
Very Fast	VF	VeryBad	VB	VeryBad			VB	Bad	Data Size		
				QoS	Signal	M		W	PR		
		VB	VB			VB					

Table 6: illustrates (Phase2) Results of Decision Type-1 and Type-2 Fuzzy Logic control rules.

QoS \ Threshold	Very Good	Good	Acceptable	Bad	Very Bad
Good	Sent	Sent	Sent	Wait	Not Sent
Medium	Sent	Sent	Wait	Not Sent	Not Sent
Bad	Sent	Wait	Not Sent	Not Sent	Not Sent

FIG.14 The 3D graphical T1-T2FLS Design between Threshold, Quality of Services, and results of decision

the best strategy to achieve the greatest stability for transferring the service to the vehicle is handling uncertainty before accepting the requests of the service [46]. interval Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Systems have the capability of coping with uncertainties [41] [45] and the outperform their counterpart the Type-1 Fuzzy Logic [44]. Type-2 Fuzzy Logic algorithm is chosen to solve the problem of uncertain processing and decision making which can combine the condition of the vehicle information's and the condition of the WFD services.

We choose Type-2 fuzzy sets to model uncertainty and imprecision in a better way, these originally presented by Zadeh in 1975, and involves procedures of fuzzification, inference, and output processing, the Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Systems were developed by Mendel and Liang [42].

XI. Results and Discussion

We had mentioned that data loss or delay is one of the most threatening things for using WFD in vehicles. For this purpose, we made a set of simulations based on the real reality of the vehicles in terms of changing their speed or direction. And apply Handover system in a program OMNET++. And the results were the loss of a lot of data.

We then took a number of steps for improvement:

Submitting a proposal regarding the volume of services provided and dividing it into small, medium and large data, such as Messages, Audio and Video stream AV stream. Pre-determine a time for each service based on the criteria for each vehicle. The results are significantly improved using the proposed T2FLS and comparing the previous scenarios with the T1FLS and T2FLS results. Referring to FIG. [15 – 20], Significant improvement appeared with the T2FLS in the average Packet Loss, Packets Delay, Received Packets, Data Size received.

FIG.15 Comparison the average Packet Loss with T1FLS and T2FLS

FIG.16 End-To-End Delay with T1FLS and T2FLS

FIG.17 Data Size received with T1FLS and T2FLS

FIG.18 Packet Drops Not Addressed

FIG.19 Packet Drops Not Addressed for Max Speed with T1FLS and T2FLS

FIG.20 Packet Drops Not Addressed for Min Speed with T1FLS and T2FLS

Conclusion and Future Work

WFD is technology recommended by Wi-Fi Alliance, which help users in Group to share services. Thus, Wi-Fi Direct can be used as application integrated in vehicles for common services, and configure a Group between V2X. WFD is suitable for a low cost, and a high data rate, therefore users can rely on WFD as an alternative and cheap solution compared to cellular networks. There are many challenges to use of WFD in vehicles, that WFD communication has a limited coverage area, the disconnection may be repeated more than once, which a distance between vehicles is frequently changed, in an environment where the vehicle is moving. Previous researches ignored the movement of vehicles and direction. Our goal is to exploit WFD among vehicles in the context of reducing dependency on network 5G. The proposal presented a set of scenarios based on different speeds of vehicles, with the change of vehicle direction and distances between vehicles. In each case, the condition of the packets is monitored in order to have an efficient, and stable communication between the vehicles.

1. This work proposed stable clustering WFDWFD based on the important parameters for Group Formation such as: location (LV) of the vehicle, destination (RV) of the vehicle, the direction (DV) of the vehicle and the speed (SV) of the vehicle.
2. This work presented some scenarios that express the condition of the vehicle on the roads, which takes into consideration of vehicle speed (0-100m/s) and direction (180°, -180°) for each scenario.
3. This work tracked the state of the packets in each scenario for calculate packets delay and loss. WFD has been proven effective, in case the vehicle speed does not exceed 60 and in the same direction. As for vehicles with speeds greater than 60m/s, they do not settle in a cluster, and all packets lose. We used OMNeT++ to scenarios simulation.
4. This work concluded from the results of previous experiments that WFD can be used with vehicles low speeds and high speeds.

In case Low Speeds, it works efficiently depending on OMNET++ results. In case High Speeds, the results are significantly improved using the proposed Type-2 fuzzy Logic System T2FLS system to model uncertainty and imprecision in a better way. Relying on T2FLS has led to a decrease in the rate of packets loss because, the selection of the available services with previously specified time in the neighboring table became more accurate and avoid uncertainty, depends on calculate the size of the data and the WFD signal strength conjunction with the distance and speed between the vehicles.

5. This work made a comparison between Type-1 and Type-2 fuzzy Logic System to improve scenarios results, and the results were as follows:

The two types of fuzzy controllers T1FLS and T2FLS behave similarly in the most cases. In the case of increasing uncertainties, T2FLS is well performed than T1FLS is terms of precision.

Therefore, WFD can be used in vehicle stations and work sites that use limited speed vehicles such as Clarks machine to alert safety and provide them with information about the devices around them. Bearing in mind that the speed of devices is limited in work areas.

In the future, we will make a real simulation of a group of vehicles, activate Wi-Fi Direct, and use services in roads, vehicle stations and work areas to get more accurate and realistic results.

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